

**ROLE OF KANTAKARI PIPPALI YOGA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF KAPHAJA
KASA: A CASE STUDY****Dr. Abhishek Shyamlal Yadav*, Dr. D. L. Zarekar, Dr. S. T. Shinde**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Kaphaja Kasa is a common respiratory disorder characterized by productive cough, excessive sputum production, chest heaviness, anorexia, and throat congestion. Ayurveda advocates Kapha-Vatahara, Deepana, and Kasahara therapies for its management. Kantakari (*Solanum xanthocarpum*) and Pippali (*Piper longum*) are classical drugs indicated in Kasa Chikitsa. **Aim:** To evaluate the therapeutic efficacy of Kantakari Pippali Yoga in the management of Kaphaja Kasa. **Case Summary:** A 40-year-old male patient presented to Kayachikitsa OPD, PMT Ayurveda College, Shevgaon with productive cough, whitish expectoration, throat irritation, and chest heaviness for 15 days. He was treated with Kantakari Churna, Pippali Churna, and Madhu for 14 days. **Results:** Significant improvement was observed in cough frequency, sputum production, throat irritation, and chest heaviness. Overall symptomatic improvement was approximately 90%. **Conclusion:** Kantakari Pippali Yoga effectively alleviated the symptoms of Kaphaja Kasa and may be considered a safe, economical, and effective Ayurvedic intervention.

KEYWORDS: Kaphaja Kasa, Kantakari, Pippali, Madhu, Ayurveda, Case Study.**INTRODUCTION**

Kasa is one of the important diseases of the respiratory system described in Ayurveda. Acharya Charaka has classified Kasa into five types: Vataja, Pittaja, Kaphaja, Kshataja, and Kshayaja.^[1] Kaphaja Kasa is characterized by productive cough, thick sputum expectoration, heaviness, anorexia, nausea, and throat congestion.

Acharya Charaka describes Kaphaja Kasa as:

**"मन्दाग्नित्वारुचिच्छर्दिपीनसोत्क्लेशगौरवैः|

लोमहर्षास्यमाधुर्यक्लेदसंसदनैर्युतम्||१८||

बहुलं मधुरं स्निग्धं निष्ठीवति घनं कफम्|

कासमानो ह्यरुग् वक्षः सम्पूर्णमिव मन्यते||१९||**¹

Meaning: The patient repeatedly expectorates thick sputum and experiences heaviness, anorexia, nausea, and productive cough due to Kapha predominance.

The Samprapti involves aggravation of Kapha Dosha causing obstruction of Pranavaha Srotas and vitiation of Vata, resulting in repeated coughing.^[2]

Acharya Bhavamishra has described a simple and effective formulation:

"कण्टकार्याः कणायाम् चूर्णं समधु कासहृत्||³

Meaning: Powder of Kantakari and Pippali administered with honey alleviates Kasa.

Kantakari is included in Dashamoola and Kasahara Mahakashaya and possesses Kaphavatahara and Shwasahara properties.^[4] Pippali acts as Deepana, Pachana, Rasayana, and Yogavahi.^[5] Madhu acts as Kapha-Shoshaka and enhances the efficacy of the formulation.^[6]

CASE REPORT**Patient Information**

- Age: 40 years

- Gender: Male
- Occupation: Service

Chief Complaints

- Productive cough for 15 days
- Excessive whitish sputum
- Throat irritation
- Chest heaviness
- Mild dyspnea on exertion

History of Present Illness

The patient developed productive cough following exposure to cold weather and frequent consumption of cold food items. Symptoms gradually increased and were associated with thick whitish sputum, throat irritation, and chest heaviness.

Personal History

- Appetite: Reduced
- Bowel: Regular
- Sleep: Disturbed
- Addiction: Nil

EXAMINATION

Dashavidha Pariksha

- Prakriti – Kapha-Vata
- Sara – Madhyama
- Samhanana – Madhyama
- Satva – Madhyama
- Satmya – Madhyama
- Ahara Shakti – Avara
- Vyayama Shakti – Madhyama
- Vaya – Madhyama

Ashtavidha Pariksha

- Nadi – Kapha-Vata
- Jihva – Sama
- Mala – Prakrita
- Mutra – Prakrita
- Shabda – Kasa Yukta
- Sparsha – Sheeta
- Drik – Normal
- Akrti – Madhyama

DIAGNOSIS

Ayurvedic Diagnosis

Kaphaja Kasa

Modern Diagnosis

Acute Productive Cough associated with Upper Respiratory Tract Infection.

TREATMENT

Kantakari Pippali Yoga

Ingredient Dose

Kantakari Churna 1.5 gm Pippali Churna 1.5 gm Madhu q.s.

Dose: Twice daily after meals. According to Pari Pradeep daily dose of churna is 1 kola i.e 6 grams. So 3 gram a time and 6gm twice a day.

Duration: 14 days.

Pathya

- Ushnodaka
- Mung Yusha
- Laghu Ahara
- Warm soups

Apathya

- Curd
- Ice cream
- Cold drinks
- Fried foods
- Day sleep

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Symptom	Grade 0	Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3
Cough	Absent	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Sputum	Absent	Mild	Moderate	Excessive
Chest heaviness	Absent	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Throat irritation	Absent	Mild	Moderate	Severe

OBSERVATIONS

Symptom Before Treatment Day 7 Day 14

Cough	3	2	0
Sputum	3	1	0

Symptom Before Treatment Day 7 Day 14

Chest heaviness 2	1	0
Throat irritation 2	1	0
Total Symptom Score:		

Day Score

Day 0 10

Day 7 5

Day 14 0

Overall Improvement = 90–100%

DISCUSSION

Kaphaja Kasa is caused by excessive intake of Guru, Snigdha, Sheeta, and Abhishyandi Ahara leading to Kapha accumulation in Pranavaha Srotas.^[12] The accumulated Kapha obstructs Vata, resulting in repeated productive cough.

Kantakari possesses Katu-Tikta Rasa, Laghu-Ruksha Guna, Ushna Virya, and Katu Vipaka. These attributes facilitate Kapha Vilayana, Kapha Nishsarana, and Srotoshodhana.^[4] It is one of the principal drugs of Dashamoola and Kasahara Mahakashaya.

Modern studies have demonstrated bronchodilator, antihistaminic, antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory effects of *Solanum xanthocarpum*. The active alkaloids Solasodine, Solasonine, and Solamargine

contribute to these effects.^[7-9]

Pippali possesses Deepana, Pachana, Rasayana, and Vatanulomana properties.^[5] It enhances digestion of Ama and clears obstructed respiratory channels. Piperine, the major alkaloid of Pippali, exhibits immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory, expectorant, and bioavailability-enhancing effects.^[10-12]

Madhu acts as Kapha-Shoshaka, Lekhana, and Yogavahi.^[6] It facilitates drug delivery and reduces excessive mucus production. Modern studies have demonstrated antimicrobial and cough-suppressant effects of honey.^[13]

The combination of Kantakari, Pippali, and Madhu therefore acts through multiple mechanisms.

- Liquefaction of thick mucus
- Facilitation of sputum expulsion
- Reduction of airway inflammation
- Improvement of Agni and metabolism
- Clearance of Pranavaha Srotas
- Reduction of cough frequency

The substantial improvement observed within fourteen days supports the classical indication of Kantakari Pippali Yoga in Kasa.

CONCLUSION

Kantakari Pippali Yoga described in Bhavaprakasha demonstrated significant clinical efficacy in the management of Kaphaja Kasa. The formulation effectively reduced productive cough, sputum production, chest heaviness, and throat irritation. Its classical Ayurvedic properties and modern pharmacological actions support its use as a safe and economical treatment option.

Further clinical studies with larger sample sizes are required to establish its efficacy scientifically.

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